

Developing and facilitating the implementation of functioning-based standards and tools for rehabilitation management and care in Europe: A collaborative effort

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Scheel-Sailer A, Selb M*, Gmünder HP, Baumberger M, Curt A, Hund-Georgiadis M, Jordan X, Stucki G; Swiss SCI/D Rehabilitation Interest Group. Towards the implementation of clinical quality management at the national level: description of current types of rehabilitation services for spinal cord injury/disorder in Switzerland using an interdisciplinary consensus process. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med.* 2022; 58(2): 190-198. DOI: 10.23736/S1973-9087.21.06923-9. *Shared first authorship

Zampolini M, Selb M*, Boldrini P, Branco CA, Golyk V, Hu X, Kiekens C, Negrini S, Nulle A, Oral A, Sgantzos M, Shmonin A, Treger I, Stucki G; UEMS-PRM Section and Board. The Individual Rehabilitation Project as the core of person-centered rehabilitation: the Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine Section and Board of the European Union of Medical Specialists Framework for Rehabilitation in Europe. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med.* 2022; 58(4): 503-510. DOI: 10.23736/S1973-9087.22.07402-0. *Shared first authorship

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SUMMARY

Background: Since the launch of the World Health Organization's Rehabilitation 2030 program, international rehabilitation professional organizations have advanced the development of functioning-based standards and data collection tools using the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF). Such standards and tools support users to organize functioning and other data in a systematic and comparable manner, that in turn, can help guide clinical assessments, intervention planning and monitoring, discharge planning as well as inform decisions about service provision across the care continuum. Moreover, functioning-based standards and tools can facilitate efforts to harmonize rehabilitation services across facilities and countries.

Objective: To develop functioning-based standards and tools and facilitate their implementation in rehabilitation management and care in Europe in collaboration with national and international rehabilitation professional organizations. The specific aims were:

- 1) to specify an ICF-based clinical assessment schedules (CLASs) for different types of rehabilitation services provided in Europe,
- 2) to develop a framework of rehabilitation service types for spinal cord injury and disorder in Switzerland (SCI/D Framework),
- 3) to develop the Individual Rehabilitation Project (IRP) framework, a functioning-based and ICF-informed patient-centred rehabilitation management framework for Europe, and
- 4) to present an executive summary of evidence that would facilitate the implementation of functioning-based standards and tools by rehabilitation practitioners and other stakeholders at different health system levels.

Methods: Specific aim 1 was addressed with study one, a multistage Delphi study comprising the development of an initial proposal, two email feedback rounds with members of the Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine Section and Board of the European Union of Medical Specialists (UEMS-PRM) and non-member PRMs, and a face-to-face deliberation. Specific aim 2 was achieved with a second study using a similar multistage consensus process with a multidisciplinary group of rehabilitation professionals in Switzerland. To pursue specific aim 3, a third study was conducted with support of a UEMS-PRM working group in which UEMS-PRM members participated in two feedback rounds and a final vote. Specific aim 4 was reached with an evidence review, a co-production with UEMS-PRM.

Results: Studies 1,2 and 3 generated functioning-based, ICF-informed patient- and interdisciplinary-oriented standards and tools: CLASs, SCI/D Framework and the IRP, respectively. The evidence review resulted in an evidence brief that clarified functioning as the foundational concept for rehabilitation, introduced the functioning-based standards and tools developed by UEMS-PRM and other rehabilitation professional organizations, and presented ways to address implementation challenges.

Conclusion: The studies and evidence brief underscore the importance of collaboration with rehabilitation professional organizations. These organizations provided insight into real-life rehabilitation practice essential for developing the functioning-based standards and tools and will be invaluable for their implementation in rehabilitation management and care in Europe.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CLAS	Clinical Assessment Schedule
ClinFIT	Functioning Information Tool
EARM	European Academy of Rehabilitation Medicine
ESPRM	European Society of Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine
European Framework	Framework of rehabilitation service types for Europe
ICF	International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health
ICF-StARS	ICF - Standardised Assessment and Reporting System of functioning information
ICSO-R	International Classification of Service Organization
InSCI	International Spinal Cord Injury Cohort Study
IRP	Individual Rehabilitation Project
ISPRM	International Society of Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine
SCI/D Framework	Framework of rehabilitation service types for spinal cord injury and disorder in Switzerland
UEMS-PRM	European Union of Medical Specialists, Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine Section and Board
WHA	World Health Assembly
WHO	World Health Organization

CHAPTER 1
Introduction

For it is not just living that is a good, but rather living well

Lucius Annaeus Seneca, Epistulae Morales

*An intelligent heart acquires knowledge,
and the ear of the wise seeks knowledge*

Proverbs 18, 15

This doctoral thesis was part of international efforts to implement functioning and the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) in rehabilitation management and care and at all levels of the healthcare. It highlights the development of specific functioning-based standards and tools for use in rehabilitation and demonstrates the importance of partnering with rehabilitation professionals and societies for developing these standards and tools.

BACKGROUND

Key concepts of the thesis

To better understand the rationale, objective and the specific aims of this doctoral these, we need to understand what is meant by the key concepts, "functioning" and "rehabilitation management and care", "standards", and "tools".

Functioning

Functioning is the third indicator of health alongside mortality and morbidity.[1] To gain a comprehensive picture of a health system's response to the health needs of people it serves and the outcome of health interventions and healthcare service delivery, having information beyond the number and causes of deaths (mortality) or the number and extent people experience certain health conditions (morbidity) is required. To complete this picture, functioning is essential.[1,2] Functioning is a term coined by the World Health Organization (WHO) to describe the dynamic interaction between a person's health condition, how well a person's bodily and mental functions work, the intactness, stability and robustness of the body structures and organs, the extent the person performs (or is able to perform) daily activities, and can participate at work, school or in the community. This interaction is impacted by the person's physical and social environment. Functioning can be operationalized with categories of WHO's International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF).[3] Figure 1 illustrates this interaction between the biopsychosocial elements of functioning. In this example, a 40-year-old man with low back pain due to an abnormal curvature of the thoracic and lumbar spine (s760) participated in a rehabilitation program (e5800). Reduced range of motion (b710) limited his ability to bend (d4105) and sit for longer periods of time (d4153). As a result, he was unable to complete tasks at work (d8451), and at home. He experienced sleep problems (b134) and was easily fatigued after physical exertion (b455) due to the pain (b280), which in turn negatively impacted his ability to handle stress (d240). Rehabilitation interventions (e5800), including medication (e1101), enabled him to return to work (d850) and do housework again (d640).

Figure 1: Biopsychosocial model of functioning underlying the ICF with low back pain as an example

Rehabilitation management and care

One of the five health strategies along with cure/treatment, prevention, promotion and palliation, rehabilitation is defined by WHO as “a set of interventions designed to optimize functioning and reduce disability in individuals with health conditions in interaction with their environment”.^[4] Negrini et al. 2022 expanded on this, providing a nuanced ICF-based definition of rehabilitation for research purposes: “multimodal, person-centred, collaborative process, including interventions targeting a person’s capacity (by addressing body structures, functions, and activities/participation) and/or contextual factors related to performance with the goal of optimizing the functioning of persons with health conditions currently experiencing disability or likely to experience disability, or persons with disability”.^[5] Although specifically developed for scientific purposes, this definition of rehabilitation impacts rehabilitation management and care as it is intended to guide rehabilitation research that supports evidence-based clinical decision-making and decision-making at other levels of healthcare.^[5]

These complementary definitions of rehabilitation help us understand what rehabilitation is. Less clear, though, are the terms “rehabilitation management” and “rehabilitation care”. As there is

currently no consensus on the definition of these terms, this thesis has adopted the following descriptions: "Rehabilitation management" focuses on the rehabilitation process that encompasses the planning, coordination, and administration of services while "rehabilitation care" focuses on the direct provision of interventions aimed at optimizing patient functioning. These descriptions were inspired by (i.e., not directly derived from) unspecified sourced descriptions suggested by the artificial intelligence platform Microsoft Copilot (<https://copilot.microsoft.com/>).

"Standard" versus "tool"

According to the Cambridge Dictionary (<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/>), a standard is "a pattern or model that is generally accepted", while a tool is "something that helps you to do a particular activity". Given these definitions, the standards and tools described in this thesis [6-8] meet both these definitions. On one hand, they are tools that users can employ for a specific activity, i.e. person-centred, interdisciplinary rehabilitation care at the micro-level of healthcare, rehabilitation management at the meso-level and standardized reporting at the micro-, meso- and macro-levels. On the other hand, they were developed to serve as a reference model or framework generally accepted by diverse stakeholders, including clinicians, researchers, hospital administrators, professional societies, and policymakers nationally and internationally.[9]

Implementing functioning hand-in-hand with the ICF

It is possible to implement the concept of functioning and functioning information without operationalising it with the ICF. For example, in an international survey conducted by Leonardi and colleagues on ICF implementation 20 years after its launch, three (Japan, South Korea and Canada) of the 14 participating countries representing WHO collaborating centres of the Family of International Classifications in four world regions reported using non-ICF-based tools.[10] These same tools, i.e., the Functional Independence Measure (FIM)[11] and the Barthel Index to assess functioning.[12] are also employed by rehabilitation hospitals in Switzerland to provide functioning information in national rehabilitation quality reports.[13] However, there are benefits to implementing functioning hand-in-hand with the ICF.

One benefit is that the ICF is open-access, meaning that it can be used by anybody for free. This has an advantage over proprietary functioning assessment tools like the FIM, especially in low-resources countries.[14,15] Other benefits are highlighted by Constand and MacDermid in their scoping review

to assess the potential use of the ICF in standardized and collaborative goal-setting.[16] They found that ICF categories were useful in rehabilitation goal-setting, as an organization tool to align patient and clinician goals as well as goals with interventions for optimizing patient functioning, and as a standard common language to ensure that patients, family and rehabilitation team members understand the goals in the same way. Moreover, as an established reference framework, the ICF can facilitate the standardization of the goal-setting approach, which in turn, can help clinicians use their time and resources more efficiently.

The ICF's status as an established, internationally accepted reference framework and its utility in standardizing functioning and other health and health-related information are also beneficial for ensuring comparability. The ICF serves as the catalyst for the first part of the Standardized Assessment and Reporting System (StARS) approach for analysing and comparing functioning information, regardless of whether the information is collected with an ICF-based or non-ICF-based tool. The first part involves linking the items/questions of the different tools to the ICF to confirm whether the items are conceptually equivalent. The second part, which will not be detailed in the present thesis, involves establishing score equivalence between the tools. Ultimately, StARS transforms the scores of conceptually equivalent tools to an interval-scaled common metric. Consequently, the transformed scores can be compared.[13,17]

Essential role of functioning and the ICF in rehabilitation

Although functioning and the ICF have been applied in areas and purposes other than rehabilitation management and care, such as education[18,19] and disability evaluation,[20,21] functioning and the ICF seem to find more resonance in the rehabilitation context. For example, the aforementioned survey of ICF implementation 20 years post-launch revealed that the ICF has been implemented in clinical settings in all 14 participating countries and predominately in a rehabilitation context and for outcome assessment.[10] This finding is also supported by ICF literature as a whole. In a recent bibliometric analysis (i.e., a statistical review of large quantities of publications to generate data on the quantity of publications, thematic trends and collaboration patterns)[22] of ICF literature published between 2002 and 2022 (i.e., 2,886 articles and 581 reviews), Stojic and colleagues identified rehabilitation as the most consistent theme addressed in the analysed publications, with a hike in frequency from 2016-2019.[23] The results of the survey and bibliometric analysis points are

likely related to the evolving global view regarding the important value and essential role of functioning and the ICF in rehabilitation.

The important value placed on functioning in rehabilitation worldwide was boosted with the 2021 paper on the global estimates of the need for rehabilitation based on the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019 in which Cieza et al. stated: "optimising functioning is the ultimate objective of rehabilitation, regardless of who the beneficiary is, who delivers it, or the context in which rehabilitation is delivered." [24] Indeed, since the launch of the ICF in 2001, [3] the concept of functioning has become a prominent fixture in the rehabilitation community and the ICF an internationally recognized standard for operationalizing functioning. [10,25-28] Furthermore, WHO's Rehabilitation 2030 initiative launched in 2017 ("Rehab 2030" from now on) [2] and the resolution on rehabilitation endorsed by the World Health Assembly in 2023 ("WHA Resolution" from now on) [29] both recognize the central role that functioning plays in the health system's response to rehabilitation patient needs with the support of the ICF. Underscoring Rehab 2030's call for integrating functioning information and using the ICF, the WHA Resolution recommends that the ICF be used "to enhance health information systems to collect information relevant to rehabilitation, including system-level rehabilitation data, and information on functioning" as one element that contributes to strengthening rehabilitation globally. The WHA Resolution states that the ICF "provides a standard language and a conceptual basis for the definition and measurement of health, functioning and disability". [29]

Developing functioning-based and ICF-informed standards and tools

Instrumental for enhancing health information systems and collecting rehabilitation-relevant information, including functioning information, and for the provision of quality evidence-based rehabilitation care is having functioning-based and ICF-informed standards and tools. "ICF-informed" is understood as the use of the ICF as a reference framework but may not necessarily be based directly on the ICF. The value of such tools has been recognized by Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine (PRM) bodies all over the world. [25,30-35] This was evident in the policy agenda 2012-2013 of the International Society of PRM (ISPRM) that included the development of ICF-based assessment tools as one of the activities to reach their strategic goal of ICF implementation in rehabilitation. [31] In Europe, the European PRM Bodies Alliance, a coalition of the Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine Section and Board of the European Union of Medical Specialists (UEMS-PRM), European Society of

PRM (ESPRM), and the European Academy of PRM (EARM), emphasizes in their 2018 edition of the White Book on PRM in Europe that functioning and the ICF are an integral part of the fabric of PRM, and indicates that ICF-based reporting tools can enable the specification of functioning domains, the consistent collection of information at different healthcare system levels and a robust comparison of functioning data from diverse information sources.[25]

Before the White Book was published, efforts had already been underway in Europe to advance systemwide implementation of the ICF under the leadership of UEMS-PRM. Acting on the decision made at the September 2015 UEMS-PRM biannual meeting to initiate a systemwide ICF implementation project, UEMS-PRM developed an implementation action plan in January 2016 at a UEMS-PRM workshop in Nottwil, Switzerland. This action plan included the development of ICF-based data collection tools in collaboration with other PRM organizations in Europe and beyond[34] and was aligned with item 3 of the ISPRM-WHO collaboration plan 2015-2017 calling for ICF-based routine data collection and national rehabilitation quality management programs.[32] UEMS-PRM understood that the most impactful way for functioning-based and ICF-informed standards and tools to be implemented in real-life rehabilitation practice is to work closely with established rehabilitation professional organizations, in part to ensure that the standards and tools developed are tailored to the real-life needs of clinicians and in part because the members of these organizations are the ones who are expected to implement the standards and tools in everyday practice.[34] To realize this implementation action step, UEMS-PRM consequently collaborated with the ICF Research Branch (www.icf-research-branch.org) to develop ICF-based standards and tools.

This PhD thesis presents two studies that were conducted as part of the scientific collaboration between UEMS-PRM and the ICF Research Branch, whose Coordinator is the author of this thesis. A third study presented in this thesis is a national adaptation of a project that was completed within the UEMS-PRM/ICF Research Branch collaboration but not presented in this PhD thesis.

OBJECTIVE

The objective of this doctoral thesis was to develop functioning-based standards and tools using the ICF as a reference system and to facilitate their implementation in rehabilitation management and care in Europe. The specific aims are to develop:

- 1) ICF-based clinical assessment schedules (CLASs) for different types of rehabilitation services currently being provided in Europe ("European Framework" from now on)

2) a framework of rehabilitation service types for spinal cord injury and disorder (SCI/D Framework) in Switzerland as a country- and condition-specific application of the European Framework

3) and the Individual Rehabilitation Project (IRP) framework, a functioning-based and ICF informed patient-centred rehabilitation management framework for Europe

and 4) to present an executive summary of evidence that would facilitate the implementation of functioning-based and ICF-informed and tools by rehabilitation practitioners and other stakeholders at different health system levels.

A brief outline of the studies and evidence brief that address these specific aims is provided in the next section. The respective peer-reviewed publications can be found in chapters 2-5.

Thesis Overview

Study 1: ICF-based clinical assessment schedule for Europe

Study 1 was conducted as part of the UEMS-PRM ICF implementation action plan.[34] Addressing specific aim 1, the first study aimed to develop an ICF-based clinical assessment schedules (CLASs) for each of the 14 rehabilitation service types contained in the European Framework, a typology of different types of rehabilitation services that was being provided all over Europe at the time of its development in 2018.[36] The European Framework can be found in the Supplementary Material. An ICF-based CLAS comprises the ICF categories, in form of ICF Core Sets[37,38] and ICF Generic Sets,[39,40] that can be assessed and reported in each of the rehabilitation service types, the patient population being assessed, the timepoint(s) for assessment and subsequent reporting of patient functioning, and the assessment tools to use.[41] The CLASs were intended to support clinical assessment planning and guide the reporting of patient functioning at assessment, during rehabilitation, and at discharge. Although the general idea of the CLAS was explored through a proof-of-concept exercise at the January 2016 Nottwil workshop,[34,41] and a version of CLASs for seven rehabilitation service types was developed in 2017 in Malaysia,[35] study 1 followed a different methodology than the one employed in Nottwil and Malaysia.

While both the Nottwil workshop and Malaysian project employed a single step consensus discussion among the stakeholders, study 1 was conducted using a multistage Delphi process comprising the development of an initial proposal, two email feedback rounds with UEMS-PRM members and non-

member PRMs, and a face-to-face deliberation during the Bi-annual UEMS-PRM Meeting in March 2019 to develop the CLASs for the European Framework. The first (so-called pre-Stockholm) Delphi round was based on the European Framework version that was in the finalization stage at the time, while the second (so-called post-Stockholm) round was completed using the finalized European Framework. The European Framework was finalized in September 2018 in Stockholm Sweden.[36]

Noteworthy is that study 1 developed CLASs for 14 rehabilitation service types, while the Nottwil workshop develop CLASs for four service types identified in the first version of the International Classification of System for Service Organization in Health-related Rehabilitation (ICSO-R),[42,43] and the Malaysian CLAS for seven rehabilitation service types provided specifically in Malaysia. Nevertheless, study 1 was informed by lessons learned from both the Nottwil workshop and the Malaysian project.

Study 2: Framework of rehabilitation service types for spinal cord injury and disorder in Switzerland

The second study addressed specific aim 2, i.e., to develop a framework of rehabilitation service types for spinal cord injury and disorder (referred to as "SCI/D Framework" from now on) in Switzerland. Study 2 used a similar multistage consensus process as study 1, this time involving a multidisciplinary group of rehabilitation professionals, specifically representatives of national medical and rehabilitation societies, representatives of international rehabilitation societies, and heads of spinal cord injury and disorder (SCI/D) specialized centers in Switzerland. This multistage development process comprised developing an initial proposal of the SCI/D Framework using the European Framework as a starting point, an email survey requesting feedback on the initial proposal, a face-to-face consensus meeting to discuss a version of the SCI/D framework modified based on the results of the survey, and a post-meeting feedback round that confirmed the final SCI/D Framework.

Developing the SCI/D Framework was not part of the UEMS-PRM ICF implementation action plan[34] but rather a country- and condition-specific adaptation of the European Framework.[36] Rehabilitation service types may differ across countries, reflecting the national health system and local healthcare context. Study 2 intended to identify the service types provided in Switzerland for SCI/D, a complex and cost-intensive health condition that has an impact over the life course and across the care continuum,[44,45] to support national clinical quality management efforts, for example to address any gaps in health care provision for persons with SCI/D. Furthermore, it had been envisioned that a CLAS for each service type contained in the SCI/D Framework would be

developed. For this, a corresponding framework of rehabilitation service types first had to be developed.

Study 3: Individual Rehabilitation Project

To pursue specific aim 3, i.e., to develop the Individual Rehabilitation Project (IRP) framework, a functioning-based and ICF-informed patient-centred rehabilitation management framework for Europe, a third study was conducted, again in collaboration with the UEMS-PRM. Although the development of the IRP framework was not named as an activity and deliverable in the original UEMS-PRM ICF implementation action plan,[34] the action plan, considered a living document, evolved to include IRP development as a key element in a broad package of standards and tools to guide the rehabilitation process. Indeed, the development of the IRP framework for Europe addressed the UEMS-PRM action plan item “development of measurement-for-improvement systems for clinical decision-making in individual patients (microlevel) and continuous improvement of a rehabilitation service (mesolevel)”.[34] Furthermore, the potential of an IRP framework for strengthening clinical rehabilitation was also highlighted in an editorial from Zampolini and colleagues that introduced an IRP model developed in Italy.[46] Although the Italian model was not based on the ICF, its principles (i.e. individualized, person-centered, interdisciplinary, focused on the optimization of functioning) served as the basis for developing the ICF-informed IRP framework for Europe in the third study.

As indicated in the aforementioned editorial,[46] a Delphi process was applied in study 3. First, a small working group of UEMS-PRM members drafted an initial version of the IRP framework for Europe in form of a paper. This paper was emailed to all UEMS-PRM members for review and feedback at the Spring and Fall 2021 UEMS-PRM meetings. Based on the revision suggestions and comments received, a revised version was reviewed by the working group, whose feedback informed a newly revised version for email feedback by all UEMS-PRM members. Afterwards, the small working group approved a pre-final version of the paper that was subsequently circulated to the UEMS-PRM members for an email vote to finalize the IRP framework for Europe. Note that the working group decided that the paper should focus on introducing the IRP and detail the framework's components, elements and variables and forego introducing the methodology for developing the IRP framework. The paper was intended as the first draft of an IRP user's manual to be employed in demonstration projects across Europe showing the use of the IRP framework (personal communication) in different rehabilitation service types outlined in the European Framework[36] and for diverse application areas.

Evidence brief on functioning-based standards and tools

Specific aim 4 was reached with an evidence brief, a co-production with UEMS-PRM, that provides an executive summary of evidence concerning the functioning-based and functioning-informed standards and tools developed by UEMS-PRM and other PRM societies. With the ultimate aim to support the implementation of these standards and tools in rehabilitation management and care at different health care levels, the evidence brief:

- clarifies functioning as the foundational concept for rehabilitation
- gives an overview of the functioning-based standards and tools developed by UEMS-PRM, including the European Framework, CLAS (study 1) and the IRP Framework (study 3), as well as standards and tools developed by ISPRM that address items in the UEMS-PRM ICF implementation action plan: the aforementioned ICSO-R[42,47] and the Clinical Functioning Information Tool (ClinFIT), an ICF-based tool for the assessment and reporting of patient functioning across the care continuum.[48] The evidence brief provides a table with a short description of each standard and tool and indicates its applicability at the micro-, meso- and macro levels of the health system.
- presents diverse applications in which functioning-based standards and tools have been used, such as the Nottwil Standard, a CLAS developed specifically for SCI rehabilitation at an SCI/D-specialized clinic in Switzerland,[49] and the use of the IRP framework in the UEMS-PRM European Accreditation of PRM Programs of Care process (<https://uems-prm.eu/new-program-application-form/>).
- calls for action in implementing the functioning-based, ICF-informed standards and tools, suggesting potential strategies for addressing implementation challenges
- highlights opportunities for facilitating implementation, such as the use of digital technologies and the burgeoning collaborations between PRM and other rehabilitation societies, academic institutions, WHO, governmental and non-governmental stakeholders.

REFERENCES

1. Stucki G, Bickenbach J. Functioning: the third health indicator in the health system and the key indicator for rehabilitation. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2017;53(1):134-8.
2. World Health Organization. Rehabilitation 2030 Initiative World Health Organization; 2017 [cited June 2025]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/initiatives/rehabilitation-2030>.
3. World Health Organization. International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2001.
4. World Health Organization. Rehabilitation fact sheet World Health Organization; 2021 [cited June 2025]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/rehabilitation>.
5. Negrini S, Selb M, Kiekens C, Todhunter-Brown A, Arienti C, Stucki G, et al. Rehabilitation definition for research purposes. A global stakeholders' initiative by Cochrane Rehabilitation. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2022;58(3):333-41.
6. Selb M, Zampolini M, Delargy M, Kiekens C, Stucki G, Study Group Clinical Assessment S. Specifying clinical assessment schedules for the European framework of rehabilitation service types: the perspective of the physical and rehabilitation medicine Section and Board of the European Union of Medical Specialists. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2019;55(6):834-44.
7. Scheel-Sailer A, Selb M, Gmunder HP, Baumberger M, Curt A, Hund-Georgiadis M, et al. Towards the implementation of clinical quality management at the national level: description of current types of rehabilitation services for spinal cord injury/disorder in Switzerland using an interdisciplinary consensus process. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2022;58(2):190-8.
8. Zampolini M, Selb M, Boldrini P, Branco CA, Golyk V, Hu X, et al. The Individual Rehabilitation Project as the core of person-centered rehabilitation: the Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine Section and Board of the European Union of Medical Specialists Framework for Rehabilitation in Europe. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2022;58(4):503-10.
9. Selb M, Zampolini M, Barotsis N, Oral A, Stucki G. The standards and tools of the European Union of Medical Specialists Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine Section and Board for rehabilitation management and care: an evidence brief for rehabilitation practitioners. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2024;60(5):729-36.
10. Leonardi M, Lee H, Kostanjsek N, Fornari A, Raggi A, Martinuzzi A, et al. 20 Years of ICF-International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health: Uses and Applications around the World. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2022;19(18).
11. Keith RA, Granger CV, Hamilton BB, Sherwin FS. The functional independence measure: a new tool for rehabilitation. *Adv Clin Rehabil*. 1987;1:6-18.
12. Prosiegel M, Böttger S, Schenk T, König N, Marolf M, Vaney C. The extended Barthel Index (EBI) – a new scale for the assessment of disability in neurological patients [in German]. *Neurol Rehabil*. 1996;1:7-13.
13. Maritz R, Tennant A, Fellinghauer C, Stucki G, Prodinger B. Creating a common metric based on existing activities of daily living tools to enable standardized reporting of functioning outcomes achieved during rehabilitation. *J Rehabil Med*. 2020;52(7):jrm00085.

14. Amatya B, Elmalik A, Song K, Lee SY, Galea MP, Khan F. Responsiveness of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability And Health (ICF) Clinical Functioning Information Tool (ClinFIT) in Routine Clinical Practice in an Australian Inpatient Rehabilitation Setting. *J Rehabil Med.* 2022;54:jrm00268.
15. Amatya B, Mukaino M, Stucki G, Selb M, Khan F. Content comparison of multidimensional functional outcome measures in rehabilitation and the ICF clinical functioning information tool: A scoping literature review. *Journal of the International Society of Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine.* 2024;7(4):144-59.
16. Constand MK, MacDermid JC. Applications of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health in goal-setting practices in healthcare. *Disabil Rehabil.* 2014;36(15):1305-14.
17. Prodinge B, Tennant A, Stucki G. Standardized reporting of functioning information on ICF-based common metrics. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med.* 2018;54(1):110-7.
18. Moretti M, Alves I, Maxwell G. A systematic literature review of the situation of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health and the International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health-Children and Youth version in education: a useful tool or a flight of fancy? *Am J Phys Med Rehabil.* 2012;91(13 Suppl 1):S103-17.
19. Vanclooster S, Van Hoeck K, Peremans L, Bilsen J, Van Der Werff Ten Bosch J, Laureys G, et al. Reintegration into school of childhood brain tumor survivors: a qualitative study using the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health - Children and Youth framework. *Disabil Rehabil.* 2021;43(18):2610-20.
20. Chiu WT, Yen CF, Teng SW, Liao HF, Chang KH, Chi WC, et al. Implementing disability evaluation and welfare services based on the framework of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health: experiences in Taiwan. *BMC Health Serv Res.* 2013;13:416.
21. Chang KH, Chi WC, Huang SW, Chang FH, Liao HF, Escorpizo R, et al. Perceptions and attitudes towards the implementation of a disability evaluation system based on the international classification of functioning, disability, and health among people with disabilities in Taiwan. *Disabil Rehabil.* 2019;41(13):1552-60.
22. Donthu N, Kumar S, Mukherjee D, Pandey N, Lim WM. How to conduct a bibliometric analysis: An overview and guidelines. *Journal of Business Research.* 2021;133:285-96.
23. Stojic S, Boehl G, Rubinelli S, Brach M, Jakob R, Kostanjsek N, et al. Two decades of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) in health research: a bibliometric analysis. *Disabil Rehabil Assist Technol.* 2025;20(2):444-51.
24. Cieza A, Causey K, Kamenov K, Hanson SW, Chatterji S, Vos T. Global estimates of the need for rehabilitation based on the Global Burden of Disease study 2019: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *Lancet.* 2021;396(10267):2006-17.
25. European Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine Bodies Alliance. White Book on Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine in Europe. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med.* 2018;54(2):125-321.
26. Maritz R, Baptiste S, Darzins SW, Magasi S, Weleschuk C, Prodinge B. Linking occupational therapy models and assessments to the ICF to enable standardized documentation of functioning. *Can J Occup Ther.* 2018;85(4):330-41.

27. World Federation of Occupational Therapists (WFOT). Position Statement: Occupational Therapy and Rehabilitation WFOT; 2019 [cited June 2025]. Available from: <https://wfot.org/resources/occupational-therapy-and-rehabilitation>.
28. Barradell S, Scholten I. How, and to what end, is the WHO-ICF framework represented in physiotherapy? Insights from a qualitative research synthesis. *Physiother Theory Pract*. 2025;41(4):792-809.
29. World Health Organization. WHO Resolution: Strengthening rehabilitation in health systems World Health Organization; 2023 [cited June 2025]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news/item/27-05-2023-landmark-resolution-on-strengthening-rehabilitation-in-health-systems>.
30. Stucki G, Qui Z, Li J, Li J, Wu X. Towards the System-wide Implementation of the ICF in Rehabilitation in China. *Chin J Rehabil Theory Pract*. 2011;17(1):5-10.
31. Imamura M, Gutenbrunner C, Stucki G, Li J, Lains J, Frontera W, et al. The International Society of Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine: the way forward - II. *J Rehabil Med*. 2014;46(2):97-107.
32. World Health Organization (WHO) and International Society of Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine (ISPRM). WHO-ISPRM Collaboration Plan 2015-2017. Unpublished document. WHO and ISPRM; 2015.
33. Stucki G. Olle Hook Lectureship 2015: The World Health Organization's paradigm shift and implementation of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health in rehabilitation. *J Rehabil Med*. 2016;48(6):486-93.
34. Stucki G, Zampolini M, Juocevicius A, Negrini S, Christodoulou N. Practice, science and governance in interaction: European effort for the system-wide implementation of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) in Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2017;53(2):299-307.
35. Engkasan JP, Stucki G, Ali S, Yusof YM, Hussain H, Latif LA. Implementation of Clinical Quality Management for Rehabilitation in Malaysia. *J Rehabil Med*. 2018;50(4):346-57.
36. Stucki G, Zampolini M, Selb M, Ceravolo MG, Delargy M, Varela Donoso E, et al. European Framework of Rehabilitation Services Types: the perspective of the Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine Section and Board of the European Union of Medical Specialists. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2019;55(4):411-7.
37. Selb M, Escorpizo R, Kostanjsek N, Stucki G, Ustun B, Cieza A. A guide on how to develop an International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health Core Set. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2015;51(1):105-17.
38. Selb M, Cieza A. ICF Core Sets. In: Bickenbach J, Cieza A, Selb M, Stucki G, editors. *ICF Core Sets: Manual for clinical practice 2nd Edition*. Göttingen, Germany: Hogrefe Publishing; 2020. p. 15-22.
39. Cieza A, Oberhauser C, Bickenbach J, Chatterji S, Stucki G. Towards a minimal generic set of domains of functioning and health. *BMC Public Health*. 2014;14:218.
40. Prodinge B, Cieza A, Oberhauser C, Bickenbach J, Ustun TB, Chatterji S, et al. Toward the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) Rehabilitation Set: A Minimal Generic Set of Domains for Rehabilitation as a Health Strategy. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil*. 2016;97(6):875-84.

41. Prodinge B, Scheel-Sailer A, Escorpizo R, Stucki G, moderators UPIW, rapporteurs. European initiative for the application of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health: development of Clinical Assessment Schedules for specified rehabilitation services. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2017;53(2):319-32.
42. Gutenbrunner C, Bickenbach J, Kiekens C, Meyer T, Skempes D, Nugraha B, et al. ISPRM discussion paper: proposing dimensions for an International Classification System for Service Organization in Health-related Rehabilitation. *J Rehabil Med*. 2015;47(9):809-15.
43. Kiekens C, Meyer T, Gimigliano F, Baffone C, Gutenbrunner CM. European initiative for the application of the International Classification of Service Organization in Health-related Rehabilitation (ICSO-R). *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2017;53(2):308-18.
44. Brinkhof MW, Al-Khodairy A, Eriks-Hoogland I, Fekete C, Hinrichs T, Hund-Georgiadis M, et al. Health conditions in people with spinal cord injury: Contemporary evidence from a population-based community survey in Switzerland. *J Rehabil Med*. 2016;48(2):197-209.
45. Gemperli A, Ronca E, Scheel-Sailer A, Koch HG, Brach M, Trezzini B, et al. Health care utilization in persons with spinal cord injury: part 1-outpatient services. *Spinal Cord*. 2017;55(9):823-7.
46. Zampolini M, Stucki G, Giustini A, Negrini S. The individual rehabilitation project: a model to strengthen clinical rehabilitation in health systems worldwide. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2020;56(1):1-4.
47. Gutenbrunner C, Nugraha B, Gimigliano F, Meyer T, Kiekens C. International Classification of Service Organization in Rehabilitation: An updated set of categories (ICSO-R 2.0). *J Rehabil Med*. 2020;52(1):jrm00004.
48. Frontera W, Gimigliano F, Melvin J, Li J, Li L, Lains J, et al. ClinFIT: ISPRM's Universal Functioning Information Tool based on the WHO's ICF. *J Int Soc Phys Rehabil Med*. 2019;2(1):19-21.
49. Scheel-Sailer A, Lampart P, Selb M, Baumberger M, Gmunder HP, Sigrist-Nix D, et al. The Nottwil Standard-Development and Implementation of an International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health-Based Clinical Standard Assessment for Post-acute Rehabilitation After Newly Acquired Spinal Cord Injury. *Front Rehabil Sci*. 2021;2:720395.

Note: The artificial intelligence platform Microsoft Copilot (<https://copilot.microsoft.com/>) was used for finding synonyms, German-English translations, and alternative wording but not for whole text passages.

CHAPTER 2

Specifying Clinical Assessment Schedules for the European Framework of Rehabilitation Service Types: The perspective of the Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine Section and Board of the European Union of Medical Specialists

Selb M, Zampolini M, Delargy M, Kiekens C, Stucki G; Study Group Clinical Assessment Schedule. Specifying Clinical Assessment Schedules for the European Framework of Rehabilitation Service Types: The perspective of the Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine Section and Board of the European Union of Medical Specialists. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2019; 55(6): 834-44.

DOI: 10.23736/S1973-9087.19.05961-6.

CHAPTER 3

Towards the implementation of clinical quality management at the national level: description of current types of rehabilitation services for spinal cord injury/disorder in Switzerland using an interdisciplinary consensus process

Scheel-Sailer A, Selb M*, Gmünder HP, Baumberger M, Curt A, Hund-Georgiadis M, Jordan X, Stucki G; Swiss SCI/D Rehabilitation Interest Group. Towards the implementation of clinical quality management at the national level: description of current types of rehabilitation services for spinal cord injury/disorder in Switzerland using an interdisciplinary consensus process. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med.* 2022; 58(2): 190-198.

**Shared first authorship*

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CHAPTER 4

The Individual Rehabilitation Project as the core of person-centred rehabilitation: the Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine Section and Board of the European Union of Medical Specialists Framework for Rehabilitation in Europe

Zampolini M, Selb M*, Boldrini P, Branco CA, Golyk V, Hu X, Kiekens C, Negrini S, Nulle A, Oral A, Sgantzos M, Shmonin A, Treger I, Stucki G; UEMS-PRM Section and Board. The Individual Rehabilitation Project as the core of person-centered rehabilitation: the Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine Section and Board of the European Union of Medical Specialists Framework for Rehabilitation in Europe. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med.* 2022; 58(4): 503-510.

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CHAPTER 5

The standards and tools of the European Union of Medical Specialists Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine Section and Board for rehabilitation management and care: an evidence brief for rehabilitation practitioners

Selb M, Zampolini M, Barotsis N, Oral A, Stucki G; UEMS-PRM Section and Board. The standards and tools of the European Union of Medical Specialists Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine Section and Board for rehabilitation management and care: an evidence brief for rehabilitation practitioners. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med.* 2024; 60(5): 729-736.

DOI: 10.23736/S1973-9087.24.08653-2.

CHAPTER 6

Discussion

The present doctoral thesis contributes to realizing the action plan of the UEMS-PRM to integrate functioning and implement the ICF in rehabilitation management and care.[1] It also highlighted the critical role of potential users (PRMs) and the importance of collaborating with PRM societies to develop functioning-based and ICF-informed standards and tools that reflect the reality of rehabilitation service provision in Europe.

This final chapter summarizes the main findings of the three studies and evidence brief. It also discusses strengths and limitations of the studies as well as potential clinical and research implications and future work related to the implementation of functioning-based and ICF-informed standards and tools for rehabilitation management and care.

MAIN FINDINGS

Study 1: ICF-based clinical assessment schedules for Europe

The first study addressed specific aim 1, i.e. to develop an ICF-based CLAS for each of the 14 rehabilitation service types contained in the European Framework.[2] UEMS-PRM members and non-member PRMs representing 33 countries across Europe participated in the two email Delphi rounds and a face-to-face deliberation. The distribution across Northern, Southern, Eastern and Western Europe was relatively even, with multiple participants in some countries. Although country participation was unevenly distributed across the Delphi rounds and final deliberation, 31 countries participated in the final deliberation to finalize the CLAS for Europe. The CLAS for each service type specified default and optional ICF Sets (generic and/or ICF Sets brief versions of ICF Core Sets).[3-6] Table 1 shows how feedback received during the development process modified a specific CLAS, exemplified by the service type "rehabilitation services at home".[2]

Table 1. Modifications to the CLAS for "rehabilitation services at home" based on the feedback received during the two Delphi rounds and the face-to-face deliberation

Development stage	CLAS proposed at each development stage <i>*revision marked in italics</i>
Initial proposal	<u>Default</u> : ICF Generic-30 + the minimal set of environmental factors[5] <u>Optional</u> : Health condition-specific ICF Core Set(s) relevant for a specific patient[4,6]
1 st (pre-Stockholm) Delphi round	Same as the initial proposal
2 nd (post-Stockholm) Delphi round	<u>Default</u> : ICF Generic-30 + the minimal set of environmental factors <u>Optional</u> : Health condition-specific ICF Core Set(s) relevant for a specific patient + <i>ICF Core Set for the geriatric population in post-acute settings</i> [7] <u>Reason for modification</u> : Rehabilitation provided in nursing homes was added to the description of "rehabilitation services at home" in the European Framework finalized in Stockholm[2]
Final deliberation	Same as the version in the 2 nd Delphi round <u>Reason for remaining the same</u> : CLAS received strong support in the 2 nd round (87% agreement from participating countries) and the comments from participants did not impact "rehabilitation services at home (including nursing home)"

Final CLAS for "rehabilitation services at home (including nursing home)"

Default: ICF Generic-30 + the minimal set of environmental factors

Optional: Health condition-specific ICF Core Set(s) relevant for a specific patient + ICF Core Set for the geriatric population in post-acute settings

As with "rehabilitation services at home (including nursing home)", all the proposals for the CLASs in the second Delphi round received moderate support (between 80-60%) or strong support (≥80%). Nevertheless, based on comments made during the second round, slight adjustments were made to the CLASs, which were presented as motions to the final deliberation participants. The final deliberation participants accepted four of these motions and introduced two additional motions for further modifications, that they also accepted after some discussion.

Study 1 focused on the first and second elements of CLAS - what to assess and report and the patient population being assessed, respectively. Regarding the third element of CLAS, i.e., the timepoint(s) for assessment, the study team proposed that functioning should be assessed at least at admission and discharge. Although the participants were asked to suggest other time points for each CLAS given the rehabilitation service type, no suggestions were received. In terms of the fourth element, i.e., the corresponding assessment tools, the study team deemed this task to be beyond the scope of the present study.

Study 2: Framework of rehabilitation service types for spinal cord injury and disorder in Switzerland

To address specific aim 2 of developing the SCI/D Framework, an initial proposal of the SCI/D Framework that was a version of the European Framework tailored to SCI/D rehabilitation in Switzerland was first generated. This initial proposal adopted all the European Framework rehabilitation service types.[2] However, two of the 14 European Framework rehabilitation service types were divided into two sub-types. "Post-acute rehabilitation – specialized" differentiated between rehabilitation provided in SCI/D-specialized centers and other specialized settings. Similarly, "specialized day rehabilitation" differentiated between rehabilitation provided in SCI/D-specialized day clinics and other specialized day clinics. Consequently, 4 sub-types were generated, expanding the SCI/D Framework to 16 rehabilitation service types. Furthermore, the descriptions were revised to include information about therapies provided and the health professional (discipline) who generally makes the referral to the service (sub-)type, in addition to the population receiving services and setting. The description of each rehabilitation service (sub-)types was further refined according to the feedback from the survey participants. These refinements included specifications about the referring health professional, the relevant quality or treatment/performance guidelines, and the physician (with medical discipline) in charge of care and coordination. As the SCI/D Framework was intended to support national quality management efforts, the detailed descriptions were additionally informed by existing Swiss quality criteria documents that were relevant for SCI/D rehabilitation (i.e., DefReha© Inpatient rehabilitation,[8] quality and performance criteria for inpatient rehabilitation,[9] outpatient rehabilitation,[10] and day clinic rehabilitation[11] from SwissReha, quality and performance criteria from Swiss Society of Paraplegia,[12] Swiss Classification of Interventions CHOP 2020,[13] and the European Association for Children in Hospital Charta.[14] This refined version of the SCI/D Framework was discussed at face-to-face consensus meeting. Other than "rehabilitation in the context of social integration", the meeting participants adopted all the rehabilitation service types. However, four service types were further split into two or three sub-types, e.g. "rehabilitation in acute care" was differentiated between newly acquired and chronic SCI/D, expanding the SCI/D Framework to 19 rehabilitation service types. Other noteworthy revisions included a broader and more inclusive definition of the responsible physician, e.g. member of SSoP was revised to "experience in spinal cord rehabilitation and treatment", and the SCI/D-specific service type of the same setting was listed first, followed by the other specialized service type and lastly the general service type. The post-meeting feedback confirmed the SCI/D Framework version resulting from the consensus meeting.

Study 3: Individual Rehabilitation Project

The third study addressed specific aim 3, i.e., to develop the IRP framework. Like with study 1 and 2, the first step in the consensus-based development process was to generate an initial proposal. The initial proposal of the IRP framework encompassed three interwoven aspects: the rehabilitation management plan, the IRP itself, and rehabilitation cycle. The rehabilitation management plan is the overarching care provision structure encompassing one or more IRPs. The IRP is a comprehensive rehabilitation management scheme that guides the rehabilitation process and contains the components basic information, Rehab-Cycle and discharge plan; has a start and an end; and comprises one or more rehabilitation cycles. The rehabilitation cycle, or Rehab-Cycle for short, is an ICF-based approach for organizing the rehabilitation process with corresponding ICF-based documentation tools.[15-17] This three-prong framework resulted from discussions that started as a search for a name for the individualized, patient-centered rehabilitation management model referred to as IRP, and eventually evolved to discussions about the need for an overarching framework around the IRP. The small working group/study team ultimately decided that developing an overarching framework would be more beneficial than focusing on the IRP alone as it would emphasize the continuity of care across the continuum from the acute, post-acute to the long-term setting, keeping in mind the CLAS (study 1). The study team also confirmed the name "Individual Rehabilitation Project" as the full name for the IRP, in line with the name of the Italian IRP model.[18] The initial proposal comprised detailed tables for the aforementioned components. Patient centeredness was underscored with variables such as shared goal-setting between patient and rehabilitation team and shared decision-making in discharge planning. Standards and tools like the European Framework,[2] ICOS-R,[19] CLAS, and ClinFIT[20] were also integrated in the IRP.

Noteworthy feedback received from UEMS-PRM members after the Spring and Fall 2021 UEMS-PRM meetings suggested further emphasizing the transition from one service to the next by explicitly recommending that the IRP of one service incorporates relevant elements from the IRP of the previous service. Accordingly, this information on the continuity between services was added to the description of the IRP. Additional UEMS-PRM members joined the small working group, who further refined the IRP framework by adding variables to the discharge component, e.g. potential architectural changes required for discharge to home. This refined version was sent to all UEMS-PRM members for a feedback round. The subsequent feedback spotlighted 3 issues: 1) the leadership and coordinative role of the PRM in the rehabilitation team, 2) the use of the terms "interdisciplinary"

versus "interprofessional", "multidisciplinary" and "multiprofessional", and 3) alter the Rehab-Cycle assessment phase[15-17] to be called "diagnosis-assessment phase". The first and second issues were resolved with the following sentence while upholding the valuable role of relevant rehabilitation professionals in the team: "...rehabilitation is generally provided by a multi-professional team under the leadership of a PRM physician, working in an interdisciplinary manner..." The third issue was addressed by adding "diagnosis of health condition" as a variable of assessment rather than to the name of the phase. The final version of the IRP Framework was approved by 45 UEMS-PRM members from 32 countries.

Evidence brief on functioning-based standards and tools

Specific aim 4 called for a summary of evidence to advance the implementation of functioning-based and ICF-informed standards and tools, particularly in routine rehabilitation practice. The evidence brief presented in this thesis met this call by disseminating targeted information about the standards and tools developed by UEMS-PRM (CLAS in study 1, IRP in study 3, European Framework of rehabilitation service types)[2] and other PRM societies (ICSO-R, ClinFIT)[19,20]. According to the evidence brief, two major challenges to implementation are 1) the lack of understanding about functioning and the use of the ICF, and 2) the lack of knowledge about existence of the functioning-based and ICF-informed standards and tools. Thus, by informing about the standards and tools, in which health care level (micro-, meso, and/or macro-level) each tool is applicable, how they have already been applied, and potential other applications, the evidence brief serves as a knowledge translation tool that has initiated a first important step toward implementation. The evidence brief also introduces other strategies to support implementation: education and training on functioning and on functioning-based and ICF-informed standards and tools, and information dissemination in the White Book on PRM in Europe,[21] in practical manuals or guidelines on how to use the standards and tools, and on electronic and social media platforms. Inadvertently, potential users also become familiar with functioning and the ICF when getting to know the functioning-based and ICF-informed standards and tools, since the information on the standards and tools are usually presented hand-in-hand with information on functioning and the ICF.

GENERAL DISCUSSION

Value of involving potential users

An essential element of the methodology employed in this doctoral thesis was stakeholder engagement,[22,23] aiming to benefit from the clinical and scientific expertise and experiences of the stakeholders. In study 1 and 3, the stakeholders were members of UEMS-PRM and other societies, and in study 2, representatives of national medical and rehabilitation societies, of international rehabilitation societies, and heads SCI/D specialized centers in Switzerland – all of whom are potential users of the resulting standard and tools. Although expert opinion is positioned low on the conventional evidence pyramid,[24] the expert opinion employed in these studies was not intended to provide information on the strength of evidence on interventions as intended by the evidence pyramid but rather to shape the functioning-based, ICF-informed standards and tools according to real-life user needs and clinical reality. This, in turn, is expected to positively influence implementation. According to the 20-country Multi-Stakeholder Engagement Consortium that explores stakeholder engagement in research and guidelines, "[stakeholder] engagement can improve the usefulness of guidelines..." and the stakeholder's duty is to "safeguard the interest of the groups the recommendations are intended to serve...".[25] In terms of impact on behaviour and outcome, Peters and colleagues in a scoping review focusing on the uptake and impact of healthcare guidelines found that half of the studies that employed stakeholder engagement experienced a positive impact.[26] As such, the experience and expertise of potential users was deemed essential to ensure the feasibility and usability of the standards and tools.

Furthermore, stakeholder engagement is generally viewed as a way to foster the uptake, for example, of research findings,[22,27] or healthcare guidelines.[25,26] Involving potential users is expected to increase their "buy-in", i.e., get their endorsement and facilitate their active engagement in implementing the standards and tools. This buy-in principle is exemplified by the uptake of the IRP framework (study 3) in the UEMS-PRM European Accreditation of PRM Programs of Care process (<https://uems-prm.eu/new-program-application-form/>). UEMS-PRM members helped shape the IRP framework; consequently, they adopted it for refining their accreditation program. This example of stakeholder engagement impact may have been influenced with what the Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research considers a contextual factor – that some roles and characteristics of individuals are more able to champion

an uptake.[28] Indeed, the persons responsible for the UEMS-PRM accreditation program were also part of the working group to develop the IRP framework.

Step forward toward implementation

The IRP framework (study 3), CLAS (study 1), the European Framework and the ICF in general have made a step forward toward implementation. For example, Santilli and colleagues followed the IRP framework to guide the rehabilitation provided in a retrospective observational study to evaluate the outcomes of chronic neurological disease patients in a non-hospitalized neuromotor rehabilitation program. Furthermore, the functioning assessments were conducted using the ICF.[29] Noteworthy is that this study also utilized artificial intelligence, specifically artificial neural networks, with consideration of the ICF assessment, among other things, to predict improvement from admission to discharge. UEMS-PRM has also been active in advocating for the implementation of the functioning-based, ICF-informed standards and tools it co-produced by including the IRP framework and CLAS in a UEMS-PRM two position papers – one on outpatient rehabilitation and another on telerehabilitation. In the position paper on outpatient rehabilitation produced through a participatory consensus of 13 European countries, Treger et al. [30] indicated as the first two general principles of professional practice in outpatient rehabilitation 1) the adherence to the ICF, specifically to the respective CLAS in defining functioning goals and 2) following the IRP framework in ensuring that the rehabilitation provided is tailored to the needs of outpatients and that the transition from one service to the next incorporates relevant elements from the IRP of the previous service. The position paper also presented the European Framework rehabilitation service types relevant for outpatient rehabilitation.[2] In the position paper on telerehabilitation produced via a Delphi process and in consideration of literature search results, Zampolini et al. outlined recommendations how the IRP framework and the ICF can be employed in telerehabilitation.[31] Although there is no guarantee that these position papers would materialize in the concrete implementation of the functioning-based, ICF-informed standards and tools, they serve as a step forward toward implementation.

Strengths and Limitations

This doctoral thesis should be considered in light of some strengths and limitations. One of the strengths of this thesis is that it was conducted in close collaboration with potential users of its results in this case UEMS-PRM and other PRM societies. As outlined in the previous section on the value of involving potential users, engaging stakeholders in the studies can facilitate implementation and has

the potential for impacting rehabilitation practice. Another strength of the thesis is its direct link to a global initiative, i.e. WHO's Rehab 2030. By responding to the Rehab 2030 call for strengthening rehabilitation and the corresponding WHA Resolution on rehabilitation, the thesis not only enjoys added legitimacy, it is also part of a larger good, with the ultimate aim of optimizing the functioning of persons and populations with a health condition. The link to Rehab 2030 and the WHA Resolution, in turn, is expected to further facilitate the implementation of the study results.

The methodology of participatory stakeholder engagement is one of the strengths of this thesis, but also pose one of its limitations. The methodology of the studies was tailored more to the practical and professional practice context of the stakeholders rather than adhering to reporting standards like Strengthening the Reporting of Observational studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) for observational studies (<http://strobe-statement.org/>) or the Conducting and Reporting of Delphi Studies (CREDES) statement.[32] Nevertheless, this does not minimize the value nor the potential impact of the study results, as the studies were conducted in collaboration with those who will translate the study results from research to practice. Another limitation is the lack of evidence supporting the utility of the standards and tools in diverse applications. For this, demonstration projects that also evaluate the benefits and challenges to using the standards and tools in diverse applications, including an evaluation of user experiences with implementing the standards and tools is needed. In line with the Learning Rehabilitation System model,[33] learnings from demonstration projects would inform about how the standards and tools work in real-life rehabilitation practice and identify issues. Stakeholders would then again be engaged to elaborate and implement solutions (e.g. updates to the standards and tools) to address these issues so that the standards and tools can achieve their purpose in facilitating rehabilitation practice. Lastly, it is unclear whether the study results are generalizable, specifically whether the resulting standards and tools are applicable beyond Switzerland in the case of study 2 and Europe in the case of studies 1 and 3. To assess this, validation studies in other geographical contexts are warranted.

IMPLICATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Clinical implications

As this doctoral thesis was conducted to execute the UEMS-PRM ICF implementation action plan, it is envisioned that the resulting standards and tools would support decision-making in rehabilitation at all levels of the health system, as shown in table 1 of the evidence brief. However, as the UEMS-

PRM is more akin to professional clinical practice, this thesis tends to highlight the clinical application of the standards and tools. One example of a clinical application is the work of Santilli et al.,[29] that has also shown the utility of the IRP framework in organizing rehabilitation provision in their exploration of outcomes of chronic neurological disease patients in a non-hospitalized neuromotor rehabilitation program in Italy. Although not a direct clinical application but rather in support of clinical work, the UEMS-PRM position paper on outpatient rehabilitation recommends that the ICF sets specified in the respective CLAS for each European Framework rehabilitation service type (study 1) be used for goal-setting.[30] According to the IRP framework (study 3), the CLASs could also be applied not only goal-setting but at all phases of the Rehab-Cycle,[15-17] such as in developing a functioning profile of the patient during the assessment phase, for monitoring outcomes during the intervention phase and for evaluating whether rehabilitation goals have been achieved in the evaluation phase. Following the Rehab-Cycle as the underpinning of the IRP framework was also highlighted in the position paper on telerehabilitation.[31] Integrating the ICF sets specified in the CLASs into existing electronic health record (EHR) systems could help streamline the workflow[34] and inform clinical decision-making through designed visualizations of the results.[35]

Research implications

The use of digital and other advance technologies, such as robotics and artificial intelligence, are increasingly becoming an integral part of rehabilitation practice today. This was made clear in the UEMS-PRM position paper on telerehabilitation.[31] Research efforts have already been undertaken to explore the use of natural language processing (NLP) to identify functioning information recorded in electronic health records (EHR) by linking free-text to the ICF.[36] There is potential for using this previous work on NLP in conjunction with the functioning-based, ICF-informed standards and tools presented in this doctoral thesis to strengthen rehabilitation as envisioned by the WHA Resolution on rehabilitation: "to enhance health information systems to collect information relevant to rehabilitation, including system-level rehabilitation data, and information on functioning, utilizing the ICF...to promote high-quality rehabilitation research, including health policy and systems research...".[37]

CONCLUSION

Functioning and rehabilitation have become more and more intrinsically linked since the launch of the ICF in 2001.[38] This doctoral thesis has further strengthened this link by conducting studies that resulted in functioning-based and ICF-informed standards and tool for rehabilitation management and care for Europe, while also bringing the UEMS-PRM ICF implementation action plan[1] to fruition. The experience of conducting the studies and the findings of this thesis have underscored the importance of partnering with PRM professional organizations, such as UEMS-PRM and ISPRM, as these organizations provide insight into real-life rehabilitation practice essential for developing the standards and tools. Engaging members of these PRM professional organizations and the organizations as a whole will be invaluable for implementing and advocating for the uptake of these functioning-based and ICF-informed standards and tools in rehabilitation management and care in Europe.

REFERENCES

1. Stucki G, Zampolini M, Juocevicius A, Negrini S, Christodoulou N. Practice, science and governance in interaction: European effort for the system-wide implementation of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) in Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med.* 2017;53(2):299-307.
2. Stucki G, Zampolini M, Selb M, Ceravolo MG, Delargy M, Varela Donoso E, et al. European Framework of Rehabilitation Services Types: the perspective of the Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine Section and Board of the European Union of Medical Specialists. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med.* 2019;55(4):411-7.
3. Cieza A, Oberhauser C, Bickenbach J, Chatterji S, Stucki G. Towards a minimal generic set of domains of functioning and health. *BMC Public Health.* 2014;14:218.
4. Selb M, Escorpizo R, Kostanjsek N, Stucki G, Ustun B, Cieza A. A guide on how to develop an International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health Core Set. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med.* 2015;51(1):105-17.
5. Prodinger B, Cieza A, Oberhauser C, Bickenbach J, Ustun TB, Chatterji S, et al. Toward the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) Rehabilitation Set: A Minimal Generic Set of Domains for Rehabilitation as a Health Strategy. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil.* 2016;97(6):875-84.
6. Selb M, Cieza A. ICF Core Sets. In: Bickenbach J, Cieza A, Selb M, Stucki G, editors. *ICF Core Sets: Manual for clinical practice 2nd Edition.* Göttingen, Germany: Hogrefe Publishing; 2020. p. 15-22.
7. Grill E, Hermes R, Swoboda W, Uzarewicz C, Kostanjsek N, Stucki G. ICF Core Set for geriatric patients in early post-acute rehabilitation facilities. *Disabil Rehabil.* 2005;27(7-8):411-7.
8. H+ Spitäer der Schweiz. DefReha 2.0 Inpatient rehabilitation: Definition and minimal requirements. [DefReha 2.0 Stationäre Rehabilitation: Definition und Mindestanforderungen] H+ Spitäer der Schweiz; 2025 [cited June 2025]. Available from: <https://www.hplus.ch/de/politik/defrehac/>.
9. SwissReha. Quality and performance criteria for inpatient rehabilitation and patients with paraplegia and tetraplegia as well as spinal cord injury sequelae [Qualitäts- und Leistungskriterien für stationäre Rehabilitation von Patienten mit einer Para- oder Tetraplegie sowie querschnittähnlicher Symptomatik] SwissReha; 2021 [cited June 2025]. Available from: <https://www.swiss-reha.com/api/rm/8P57Y3J8J28SFND>.
10. SwissReha. Quality and performance criteria for outpatient rehabilitation [Qualitäts- und Leistungskriterien für ambulante paraplegiologische Rehabilitation] SwissReha; 2015 [cited June 2025]. Available from: <https://www.swiss-reha.com/api/rm/D746J2P46J6TST2>.
11. SwissReha. Quality and performance criteria for day clinic rehabilitation [Qualitäts- und Leistungskriterien für teilstationäre paraplegiologische Rehabilitation] SwissReha; 2015 [cited June 2025]. Available from: https://www.swiss-reha.com/de/ambulant_teilstationaer.html.
12. Swiss Society of Paraplegia (SSoP). Quality and performance criteria for the treatment of patients with paraplegia or tetraplegia as well as spinal cord injury sequelae [Qualitäts- und Leistungskriterien für die Behandlung von Patienten mit einer Para- oder Tetraplegie sowie mit querschnittähnlicher Symptomatik] SSoP; 2018 [cited June 2025]. Available from: {European Association for Children in Hospital (EACH), 2016 #44}.
13. Swiss Federal Statistics Office. Swiss Classification of Interventions CHOP 2020 [Schweizerische Operationsklassifikation CHOP 2020] Swiss Federal Statistics Office; 2019 [cited June 2025]. Available from: <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/de/home/statistiken/kataloge-datenbanken/publikationen.assetdetail.9286160.html>.

14. European Association for Children in Hospital (EACH). EACH Charta EACH; 2016 [cited June 2025]. Available from: https://each-for-sick-children.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/EACH-Charter-Articles_Adults_DEU.pdf.
15. Rauch A, Cieza A, Stucki G. How to apply the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) for rehabilitation management in clinical practice. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2008;44(3):329-42.
16. Swiss Paraplegic Research and Swiss Paraplegic Centre. ICF case studies: Translating interventions into real-life gains – A Rehab-Cycle approach Swiss Paraplegic Research; 2015 [cited June 2025]. Available from: <https://www.icf-casestudies.org/case-studies>.
17. Stucki G, Bickenbach J, Selb M, Melvin J. The International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health. In: Frontera W, editor. *DeLisa's Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation Principles and Practice*. 6th ed. Philadelphia: Wolters Kluwer; 2019. p. 208-26.
18. Zampolini M, Stucki G, Giustini A, Negrini S. The individual rehabilitation project: a model to strengthen clinical rehabilitation in health systems worldwide. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2020;56(1):1-4.
19. Gutenbrunner C, Nugraha B, Gimigliano F, Meyer T, Kiekens C. International Classification of Service Organization in Rehabilitation: An updated set of categories (ICSO-R 2.0). *J Rehabil Med*. 2020;52(1):jrm00004.
20. Frontera W, Gimigliano F, Melvin J, Li J, Li L, Lains J, et al. ClinFIT: ISPRM's Universal Functioning Information Tool based on the WHO's ICF. *J Int Soc Phys Rehabil Med*. 2019;2(1):19-21.
21. European Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine Bodies Alliance. *White Book on Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine in Europe*. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2018;54(2):125-321.
22. Concannon TW, Meissner P, Grunbaum JA, McElwee N, Guise JM, Santa J, et al. A new taxonomy for stakeholder engagement in patient-centered outcomes research. *J Gen Intern Med*. 2012;27(8):985-91.
23. Deverka PA, Lavalley DC, Desai PJ, Esmail LC, Ramsey SD, Veenstra DL, et al. Stakeholder participation in comparative effectiveness research: defining a framework for effective engagement. *J Comp Eff Res*. 2012;1(2):181-94.
24. Murad MH, Asi N, Alsawas M, Alahdab F. New evidence pyramid. *Evid Based Med*. 2016;21(4):125-7.
25. Petkovic J, Magwood O, Lytvyn L, Khabisa J, Concannon TW, Welch V, et al. Key issues for stakeholder engagement in the development of health and healthcare guidelines. *Res Involv Engagem*. 2023;9(1):27.
26. Peters S, Sukumar K, Blanchard S, Ramasamy A, Malinowski J, Ginex P, et al. Trends in guideline implementation: an updated scoping review. *Implement Sci*. 2022;17(1):50.
27. Boaz A, Hanney S, Borst R, O'Shea A, Kok M. How to engage stakeholders in research: design principles to support improvement. *Health Res Policy Syst*. 2018;16(1):60.
28. Damschroder LJ, Reardon CM, Widerquist MAO, Lowery J. The updated Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research based on user feedback. *Implement Sci*. 2022;17(1):75.
29. Santilli G, Mangone M, Agostini F, Paoloni M, Bernetti A, Diko A, et al. Evaluation of Rehabilitation Outcomes in Patients with Chronic Neurological Health Conditions Using a Machine Learning Approach. *J Funct Morphol Kinesiol*. 2024;9(4).
30. Treger I, Oral A, Giustini A, Christodoulou N, Ceravolo MG, Zampolini M. Physical and rehabilitation medicine for outpatients. The European PRM (UEMS PRM Section) Position Statement. *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2025;61(1):4-8.

31. Zampolini M, Oral A, Barotsis N, Aguiar Branco C, Burger H, Capodaglio P, et al. Evidence-based position paper on Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine (PRM) professional practice on telerehabilitation. The European PRM position (UEMS PRM Section). *Eur J Phys Rehabil Med*. 2024;60(2):165-81.
32. Junger S, Payne SA, Brine J, Radbruch L, Brearley SG. Guidance on Conducting and REporting DElphi Studies (CREDES) in palliative care: Recommendations based on a methodological systematic review. *Palliat Med*. 2017;31(8):684-706.
33. Bickenbach J, Rubinelli S, Sabariego C, Stucki G. The Learning Rehabilitation System: Strengthening an intersectoral strategy to improve functioning of an ageing population. *Health Policy*. 2023;135:104866.
34. Chan EKH, Edwards TC, Haywood K, Mikles SP, Newton L. Implementing patient-reported outcome measures in clinical practice: a companion guide to the ISOQOL user's guide. *Qual Life Res*. 2019;28(3):621-7.
35. Bachmann JM, Shiflet MA, Palacios JR, Turer RW, Wallace GH, Rosenbloom ST, et al. Patient-Reported Outcome Measures in Routine Clinical Practice: Practical Guidance for Institutional Review Boards. *Ethics Hum Res*. 2024;46(4):27-37.
36. Newman-Griffis D, Maldonado JC, Ho PS, Sacco M, Silva RJ, Porcino J, et al. Linking Free Text Documentation of Functioning and Disability to the ICF With Natural Language Processing. *Front Rehabil Sci*. 2021;2.
37. World Health Organization. WHO Resolution: Strengthening rehabilitation in health systems World Health Organization; 2023 [cited June 2025]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news/item/27-05-2023-landmark-resolution-on-strengthening-rehabilitation-in-health-systems>.
38. World Health Organization. International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2001.

Note: The artificial intelligence platform Microsoft Copilot (<https://copilot.microsoft.com/>) was used for finding synonyms, German-English translations, and alternative wording but not for whole text passages.